

Quick Challenge-Driven, Human-Centred Co-Creation Mechanism for INDUStry-Academia Collaborations

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PROJECT GOAL

INDUSAC's main objective is to develop and validate a state-of-the-art, Industry-Academia Collaboration mechanism for quick, challenge-driven, human-centred co-creation.

The INDUSAC project designs a state-of-the-art mechanism for industry-academia collaboration that is based on human-centred design principles that enable quick project co-creation. At least 300 international co-creation projects are selected for implementation to ensure the validation of the mechanism. These micro-projects led by teams consisting of students, researchers, and company staff cover various activities to target numerous industrial sectors. They are expected to create a bridge between business and academia.

METHODOLOGY

The aim of the methodology is to facilitate the creation of company, student and researcher teams by matching industry needs with students and researchers interests and skills. The methodology is built on a baseline of pre-existing co-creation approaches and offers guidance packages, as well as processes and tools for its smooth functioning. It provides detailed user journey maps

THE INDUSAC CONCEPT

1000
companies

3000
students

300
researchers

PLATFORM

The aim of the platform is to build on pre-existing Industry-Academia Collaboration mechanisms to facilitate a user-friendly co-creation process. It provides the foundation for developing solutions that clearly process the needs and interests of companies, students, and researchers in the EU.

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